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THE INCLUSIVE EDUCATION OF CHILDREN WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITIES IN GREECE

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Abstract

This paper examines the legal framework of Inclusive Education (IE) of children with Intellectual Disabilities in Greece through the passage of time and the challenges that those disabled students confront into the social and educational context. Additionally, in this study a comparative research about Inclusive Education between European and non-European countries is presented, in which children with Special Educational Needs (SEN) and more specifically with Intellectual Disabilities are served under different education and social policies and laws. In conclusion, it's described that IE aims on the holistic development of children with disabilities in all environments.

Keywords: inclusive education, intellectual disabilities, Greek educational system.

1. Introduction

The 20th century has been internationally significant for Special Education Needs (SEN). The negative attitude and prejudices that it had society in previous years towards people with disabilities began to be eradicated. The institutions of custodial care and educational practices on people with Intellectual Disabilities (ID) were replaced by new humanitarian, educational and psychosocial practices. Those people were treated as a weak and powerless group as if they hadn't had any psychosocial and learning need but only basic functional lifelong needs. For this reason, international organizations tried to provide primarily the rights of those disabled people instead of engaging them in the schooling practices in order to develop their abilities and their learning skills and to have equal access to all environments (Miles, & Singal, 2010).

With the passage of time, that perspective was superseded by a new educational philosophy that would provide the development and the empowerment of academic, social, psychological and physical skills of ID people. In this change, key role had the reauthorization of the legislation and the various specific educational programs for people with significant intellectual disabilities. Those programs enable those children to overcome their barriers and having access to the general curriculum.

The main goal now becomes the right of participation of all children in the general education system. Thus, Barbra and Joyline (2014) have pointed out that the educational provision has been changed from exclusion to inclusion. The new education Act Amendments for Individuals with Disabilities (IDEA) of 1997 and the abstract of No Child Left Behind Act (NCLB) of 2001 that revised the Education Act of 1965, signaled an educational system that is compulsory and free for every child. Also, the regulation provides that educational programs will focus not only on the life and functional skills, but on the peculiarities and the individual learning needs of each student with Intellectual Disabilities separately (Heward, 2011).

In this way, new terms such as «inclusion» and «integration» were realized after the World Special Education Congress in Salamanca in 1994 (Barbra, & Joyline, 2014). The Jomtien's and Salamanca's conferences outlined the need of inclusion on students with intellectual disabilities according to their achieving grade-level standards.

In this study therefore, we sought to examine the inclusive education of children with intellectual disabilities in the Greek educational system through the passage of the time.

2. Inclusion of children with Intellectual Disabilities

The last two decades the philosophy and policies regarding the education of children with SEN have made a great process in the field of integration and inclusion. The concept of “inclusion” encompasses educational and social policy initiatives (Symeonidou, 2015). The Jomtien’s and Salamanca’s conferences highlights the need either to provide education for all children in a general school and education for students with intellectual disabilities according to their achieving grade-level standards or to reduce all types of exclusion and discrimination (Vaz, et. al. 2015). It is noteworthy, that those grade-level standards of children with ID differ from their achieving grade-level standards because of the discrepancy between the chronological age of intellectual disabled children and their mental age. Within this perspective, the specialists focus on the educational needs of those marginalised groups and use alternate and multisensory methods according to the alternate achievement standards’ of those students (Barbra, & Joyline, 2014; Miles, & Singal, 2010).

As a result, the implementation of Inclusive Education (IE) of children with ID in general schools has been a goal in many countries. Inclusion provides equal access to all children on academic, social, psychological and physical environments, irrespective of the race, gender, colour, severity or the type of the disability of the pupils. In Greece, the educational legacy and policy has promote the IE of children with ID in general educational settings, but the progress in practice can only be described as slow (Grammenos, 2013; Tsiantis, Diareme, Giannakopoulou, & Soumaki, 2006). Unless IE in Greece has been influenced by practices and policies of other countries, it can not have the similar evolvment with those industrialised countries (Armstrong, Armstrong, & Barton, 2016).

However, with the passage of the time the IE has gone through several stages as the percentage of children who have Special Educational Needs (SEN) and is served under Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA), seemed to differ into European and American countries. More specifically, that percentage varies from 1% in Greece to 18% in Finland, when that percentage estimate to 13% in America (European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education, 2018; Brusling, & Pepin, 2003). As it could be expected, effective factors in IE as population density and the socioeconomical development of the countries pointed out the correlation between those limitations and the percentage of students that have SEN in Europe and other continents and countries, such as USA.

For that reason, the European countries adopted three different approaches in IE. More specifically, the West and South European countries such as Greece, Spain, Italy, Cyprus etc. adopted the one-track approach aiming the inclusion of almost all students; the North and West European countries such as United Kingdom, Ireland, Finland, Denmark, Austria etc. adopted the multi-track approach, where the students could receive education between the general education system and the SNEs; Finally, Switzerland and Belgium adopted the two-track approach, which offers two distinct educational systems, the mainstream system and the separate school and the separate special classes for students with disabilities (Brusling, & Pepin, 2003).

Furthermmore, according to the USA education policies, the government served under Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) the eligible of 3 to 21 years old students with free and appropriate public school education. The U.S. Department of Education (2017) has documented that 95% of 6 to 21 years old students with disabilities spent more than 80% of their school days in regular classrooms. Also, 3% percent of the students attended an inclusion school, 1% in a regular private school initiated by their parents and less than 1% in a separate residential or correctional facility, in a homebound or in a hospital. Additionally, a statistical analysis by the U.S. Department of Education (2017) in school year 2015–16 has accounted that 34% of all students that

served under IDEA had Specific Learning Disabilities (SLD), and 5 to 9% has ASD, ID, emotional disorders and developmental delays.

Moreover, a percentage of 49.5% of the students with ID is served in general class, 26.6% in a separate school for students with disabilities, and 23,8% received special education services on separate residential or correctional facility, in regular private school, or in hospital placement.

Unfortunately, in the last decade there is no data base on the percentages and on the special education services that received people with ID in Greece compared to Europe (EU) and World Health Organization (WHO) data sources (Grammenos, 2013). In 2006, Tsiantis, Diareme, Giannakopoulou, and Soumaki have pointed out that the statistical informations inform that only 2,859 children with mild to moderate ID in academic year 2002-2003 have access in the education system, while most children with severe ID can't participate in those educational programmes. Three years later in 2005–2006, 2389 students with ID were served in pre-school and primary education system (Ministry of Education, 2008). The most recent results about IE generally in Greece was in 2018 by the Education and Training Monitor, which informed us that from 75680 students with special needs, only 10883 students received education in special classrooms.

2.1. Inclusion of children with Intellectual Disabilities in Greece

In contemporary Greece, the interest on the SENs and more specifically on intellectually disabled individuals was first expressed by Imbrioti, Exarchopoulos and Melanitis in the early 20th century (Panteliadou, 2017). Until that time, the families and the charitable communities had the primary responsibility for the education and care of those disabled children (Miller, Morfidi, & Soulis, 2013).

In 1906, was first founded the "House of Blind individuals" and in 1923 "The School for Deaf Students" which offered health and educational services on students. But, a few years later in 1937 the Greek government founded in Athens the first special school for intellectual disabled students.

For those who were disabled, the philanthropy, the church and the charity were the only driving forces, which protected them and had the responsibility of those people with disabilities. But on the other hand, those charitable and health organizations limited their opportunities and gave them less opportunities comparatively to typically developing children. Those children were not part of the social or the educational system as they were restricted, excluded from the general classrooms and educated in separate institutions. With the passage of the time those separate institutions became ultimately special schools which adopted initially a medical model of approach.

This meant that, the medical institutions tended to see disability as a bodily problem, which required a medical solution rather than a social problem. Within that perspective the doctors used to confront the disabled people as individual entities which needed to be fixed and not as a social unit which needed to have equal access to all kind of positions. As a result, the medical model view ignored the social integration of those people, their equal access in education, health, accommodation and transportation and relied only on their limitations. On the contrary, those people tended to suffer high rates of exclusion and discrimination in all societies and in all kinds of environments. Additionally, the doctors and the special educators focused on determining, measuring and quantifying the differences of those children by using various psychometric tools and tests and that practice increased the gap between their education, their achieving grade-level standards, their relations between their same age peers, their teachers and finally their inclusion in the societies (Retief, & Letšosa, 2018). Indeed, many educators were concerned with how to providing diagnostic and/or classification labels for children and not how to make adaptations and modifications in the academic curriculum in order to provide them in the general education environment and make it more accessible to them. The exposure and the involvement of those children in the general education system will help them to interact more effectively with the people and the society. Thus, students with Intellectual Disabilities should be taught academic and not only

domestic or functional activities in general settings in order to enhance and encourage them to participate effectively in all environments.

Nevertheless, in 1981 the Greek government enacted its first legislation, the Law 1143/1981, which provided that all disabled students have the right for free and public school access on education and on health services. Since the Greek State has been a full member of the European Union in 1980, it has tried to harmonize the Greek and European legislation and policy, ensuring equal social participation, independent living and economic autonomy of disabled people and of people with SENs. In that context, this perspective highlights the transition from institutionalized care to educational, social and professional inclusion of people with disabilities and especially with ID (European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education, 2018).

Twenty years later, the Law 2817/2000 describes that attempt to organically integrate the special education into overall education and social framework. A few years later, the law 3699/2008 underlines the need of inclusion of disabled pupils into regular environments with or without support. Additionally, that legislation established that the education for the students with severe or less severe disabilities is compulsory. If those students have severe difficulties, they would be served under special schools by providing their learning, cognitive, emotional, and social process and development (European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education, 2018).

After four years, in May 2012 the Greek Committee affirm and adopt all pertinent United Nations directives. These policies include the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) and provided the try of progressing and empowering the participation of those disabled students in general schools. Furthermore, a more recent law in 2016 (4368/21.02.2016 (article 82) provides the IE and the need for close co-operation between general and special schools. All children with or without disabilities should be educated in a general class by well educated inclusive and general class teachers (European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education, 2018). Indeed, the Greek legacy sets out that students with disabilities are educated in a regular classroom *“support by the class teacher, or with individualised parallel support co-education, provided by a special education teacher. Moreover, students can be served by an inclusion teacher who may support one or more pupils in the class in co-operation with the class teacher or in an inclusive class”* (Law 4368/2016, article 82).

That adoption, embodies the Social Model of the Disability, which aims to end people’s exclusion. It is noteworthy that those disabled students do not need to change their life but they have the same opportunities as non-disabled students. Thus, the Social Model of Disability recommended an explanation of the Disabled people’s life experience in society, which responds to their individual needs. This approach was developed as a new way of thinking, which understands and sees the disability as a human right that gives equal, free, and inclusive primary and secondary education to all children according to their needs (Berghs, Atkin, Hatton, & Thomas, 2019).

The teachers are committed to adapting their teaching methods to suit the child’s individual needs and different speeds of learning. The children with disabilities can participate equally to all activities and that contributes to their full development of their self-worth, human potential and sense of dignity. At the same time, children who have no obvious disabilities can benefit from the learning of certain subjects, which teachers have acquired for their disabled learners. Indeed, inclusive schools aim to provide assistance, respect and understanding between the disabled and non-disabled learners and overcome the stigma of disability (Retief, & Letšosa, 2018).

3. Conclusions

Finally, in some countries such as in Greece, Inclusive Education also means skills, relations, attitudes and teachers and parents' expectations that need to be changed in promoting the holistic development of all their children in the society. It results as a dynamic relationship between a teacher and a learner, between learners themselves and between schools and families. Inclusive schools aim to build system support services and communities in which teachers, parents and local community leaders will provide a better quality of life for every child. It is a very difficult, challenging and ongoing struggle, which schools, teachers, parents and even learners themselves face daily. The lack of money and resources, the stigma that parents need to overcome, the incomplete training, guidance and support of the teachers are only part of the problem (Retief, & Letšosa, 2018). The children with SEN have to deal with several resistances from different systems and environments. But it is certain that we need to rethink about inclusive schooling, the real purpose of education and how important is for children to learn all together as the IE opens up many opportunities which we could not even imagine.

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